

NEGATIVE CONSEQUENCES OF MORE EATING AND RECOMMENDATIONS ON EATING

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ABSTRACT

The nutritional status of the population is one of the factors affecting the health of the population, secondly, the planning and rational organization of nutrition is of great economic importance, and thirdly, in a market economy, the identification of needy groups and social assistance is one of the indicators of state welfare. is

Healthy and orderly nutrition is one of the most effective factors in preventing occupational diseases and preventing the negative effects of the external environment in environmentally unfavorable conditions.

According to the world's leading scientists, in recent years, atherosclerosis has been diagnosed among people in their 20s and 30s. According to them, the main reason for this is the lack of adherence to a healthy lifestyle. Some young people are sedentary, spend a lot of time around the computer, do not follow a eating routine, and abuse alcohol and nicotine. In the early stages of sclerosis, sometimes unexplained weakness occurs. In addition, there is sensitivity, apathy, rapid fatigue, inability to work at the end of the day, rapid nervousness. Then memory and attention decline, and the person has difficulty moving from one activity to another. As a result of deteriorating attention, mistakes are made, and productivity decreases. In this case, it is necessary to regulate nutrition, work and rest. Foods should be free of shavel and uric acid.[1.2.3.]

It is necessary to reduce the consumption of cocoa, chocolate, black tea, spinach, oatmeal, sprats, sardines, all kinds of meat, alcohol and quit smoking. Dairy products, on the other hand, should always be on the diet. Fruits, vegetables, legumes, eggs, cheese, bread are also helpful. Consumption of table salt should also be reduced.

Many women complain of weight gain after the age of 30. They maintain a varied diet, engage in light sports, but do not lose body weight, as a decrease in metabolism is observed at this age. It is recommended to wake the body to prevent this condition from occurring. To do this, eat fruit, protein and fiber-rich foods for breakfast. It allows the body to be supplied with enough energy during the day and gives a feeling of satiety for a long time. Lunch, on the other hand, is ordered to avoid high-calorie foods. Consumption of pasta, sandwiches,

potatoes, sweets is limited. It is recommended to eat salads, tomatoes, cucumbers, bell peppers made from large quantities of coconuts. Instead of sweets after dinner, you should eat dairy products, kefir, yogurt, cottage cheese.[4]

This, along with reducing the feeling of hunger, overcomes fatigue.

People over the age of forty are recommended to eat as follows:

- Women's diet should be nutritious and contain all the nutrients - proteins, fats, carbohydrates, vitamins and minerals.[6]

- Nutrients should be in a balanced ratio and slightly reduce the capacity of the ration. It is important to reduce the intake of foods high in carbohydrates and fats, animal fats and other sources of cholesterol. To slow down the absorption of excess carbohydrates in the intestine, the diet should be rich in fiber-containing substances. Fibers cause a feeling of exhaustion without being digested, tickling the nerve endings in the intestinal wall increases its movement, reducing the absorption of carbohydrates. Cereals, coarse-grained bread, pasta made from durum wheat, legumes, vegetables, mushrooms and fruits contain large amounts of dietary fiber.[5]

- Women's diet should include milk and dairy products, various fish and seafood, meat, eggs, various cereals, bread (preferably from large grains). Fruits and vegetables, especially leaf-shaped vegetables, which provide the body with a complex of vitamins and minerals, are a mandatory and widely available component of the diet.

It is advisable to approach nutrition as follows:

- Drink half a glass of water or unsweetened juice before meals;

- Variety of dishes - variety;

- Adequate food;

- Eat small but frequent meals (every 2.5 to 3.0 hours), controlling the amount of food you eat in one meal;

- Reducing the consumption of easily digestible carbohydrates (sugar, milk chocolate, jam);

- Do not drink bitter tea or coffee, but do not limit other liquids, it is better to drink 1.5 - 2.0 liters of boiled chilled water or liquid coke tea per day;

- Food should be chewed and eaten slowly. This has a positive effect on his digestion and arouses a feeling of rapid exhaustion;

- Avoid eating (especially slippery food) less than 3 hours before bedtime.

Dietary recommendations for people over 50 years of age.

During this period, biologically active substances, vitamins, macro-and micronutrients should be adequately consumed.

The occurrence of this deficiency can be caused by internal factors (diseases of the stomach, intestines, liver and other organs) that prevent them from getting enough into the body with food or in moderation. The need for vitamins does not decrease, especially in women over 50 years of age. On the contrary, their insufficient fall complicates the processes taking place in the female body and creates the basis for the appearance of menopause. Lack of vitamin A (retinol) or its substitute - carotene in the diet of women reduces the ability to see and the protective properties of the organism. Calciferol (vitamin D) deficiency leads to the development of osteoporosis because it regulates the absorption of calcium in the body. The antioxidant tocopherol (vitamin E) is

essential to support the endocrine function of the ovaries.

Riboflavin (vitamin B2) and pyridoxine (vitamin B6), which regulate all metabolic processes, are also important for the body to function normally. Vitamin PP deficiency leads to the formation of stress and mental illness, while cyanocobalamin (vitamin B12), choline (vitamin B4), inositol (vitamin B8), as well as folic acid deficiency (vitamin B9) increase the likelihood and accelerate the development of atherosclerotic processes.

The World Health Organization recommends consuming 500 grams of fruits and vegetables a day. But despite the fact that our country is rich in them throughout the year, our people receive them on average around 100-200 grams.

This causes a deficiency of vitamins and various micro and macronutrients in the body.

Bone tissue density in women and men begins to decline between the ages of 40 and 50. However, with the onset of menopause in women, this process accelerates, the important factor that regulates calcium metabolism in the female body disappears, resulting in the use of individual calcium distributed in the bones. Osteoporosis (gradual mortal fracture of the bones) is sometimes called cataract pain. Bone absorption occurs slowly. Due to this, the disease is initially characterized by no pain and no complaints. Its symptoms occur after a fracture due to a decrease in bone density.

Calcium is vital not only because it keeps bones at a normal level, but also because blood vessels and its tissues are in dire need of it. This microelement slows down the growth of tumors (cancer), eats away cholesterol plaques, cleanses the arteries,

maintains the activity of the nervous system.

Calcium depletion is directly related to the presence of phosphorus in the body. That is why this process is called calcium-phosphorus metabolism. If there is a lot of calcium in the diet and not enough phosphorus, then the excess calcium is eliminated from the body. In order to ensure a balanced reduction of phosphorus and calcium, a person needs not only these substances, but also sufficient amounts of vitamin D. Depletion of phosphorus depends on the amount of iodine, fluorine, cobalt, iron, magnesium in the body.[7]

The balance of calcium and magnesium in the body is of great importance. On the one hand, magnesium is necessary for the body, because in its deficiency the amount of calcium in the walls of blood vessels increases, and they become mortal and prone to spastic contractions. However, an excess of magnesium also has a negative effect on the depletion of calcium and phosphorus. Therefore, it is recommended that the ratio of calcium and magnesium in the diet be 1: 0.5.

Source of calcium and phosphorus - dairy products (cheese, cottage cheese, milk) have a high biological relief, with which more than 70% of calcium falls. Calcium is also found in leaf-shaped green vegetables, soy products, almonds, and hazelnuts. It is advisable to consume more dairy products. Low-fat cheeses and low-fat cottage cheese should be on the table every day. Also, as mentioned above, vegetables and fruits are the main source of minerals. Only 40% of the iron in cereals, peas and nuts is reduced in the body.

In short, nutrition is a biological need of every human being and it is related to a number of medical, social, economic and

environmental issues. Adherence to the rules of proper nutrition is one of the main

and important factors that ensure a person's health throughout life.

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